

The GATE
Interim Report
(May 2023 – December 2024)

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and contribution from the NERQ_OS group

1 The Open Science Learning Gate

This [Open Science Learning Gate \(GATE\)](#) interim report on the planning phase provides an overview of the initiative's progress. It covers the initiative's first ideas of the [NERQ_OS Group](#), steps achieved, ongoing actions, and future strategies. The report aims to present a comprehensive description of the initiative's current state, focusing on stakeholder engagement and the development of the GATE. By documenting these early-stage aspects, we aim to ensure transparency, uphold the principles of open science, and invite collaborators to join the initiative.

The GATE, an innovative intersection for the promotion and norm-setting of Open Science (OS) (via experts), sprung forth from the high expertise and vision of the NERQ_OS group ([Network for Education and Research Quality - Open Science Group](#)). To be developed as a key resource to collect and foster high-quality training on Open Science for all important actors in the Open Science ecosystem, the GATE exemplifies an ambitious effort to support training enhancement, capacity building, and identify and set norms in this field.

The GATE idea leverages a collecting, screening and reflecting process to ensure that the educational resources and training shared are of the highest quality and meet current norms. The added emphasis on empirical data collection from training experts in the research community and their majority agreement on guidelines inclusion only reinforces the credibility and reliability of the GATE. The GATE will publish its current knowledge base on Open Science Guidelines and principles in an Open Access GATE report each year starting in 2025/2026.

2 The Idea of the Open Science Learning Gate

The GATE supports professionalisation (based on commonly agreed standards) and high-quality, customised OS training within research and higher education. It is an intersection of OS training resources in line with OS principles supported by the research community and tailored to the needs of various OS learning groups.

The GATE invites the research community to participate in creating this intersection and thus pave the way for identifying norms and possible guidelines of OS (training).

We adapted and modified the [OS actor's classification of the European Science Cloud](#) (p.17) to start the

- A. TAILORED intersection of OS training. The GATE takes the needs of various OS actors into account. It harmonises and supports
- B. HIGH-QUALITY OS training based on the research community's principles of responsible conduct of research, namely research integrity, research ethics and ethics of artificial intelligence tools operating with OS resources. To use and be part of this intersection, OS trainers are invited to join via the GATE and to
- C. COMMUNICATE as experts which guidelines are addressed in their training (representing specific OS stakeholders) and
- D. Assess and, if necessary, amend their training to reflect the current status quo the research community sets.
- E. By including at least 80% of the current principles reported by the community via the GATE, trainers can BADGE their training as high quality and CONNECT their OS training via

the GATE to their community. The GATE, therefore, has the potential to disseminate training that meets the current requirements of OS practices.

- F. Data collection via the GATE is an ongoing process that considers rapidly changing research practices, thus enabling continuous development of norms and updating and training professionalism.

The NERQ_OS group started early collaborations to enhance the GATE's functionality further. In line with this, Charité and FORRT initiated the first talks, with the latter particularly interested in connecting the GATE's assessed training from target group researchers to their curated list of OS training. These first collaborative efforts were followed by more collaborative talks regarding target groups 2-12 at the WCRI2024 and afterwards.

In December 2024, the GATE became an intersection and was actively connected to the FORRT collection for all training materials related to researchers and students. We are also in contact with the EOSC—EU Node to be connected to the training catalogue for the training materials related to Data Curators, Data Stewards, Data Librarians, and OS Educators.

3 Steps achieved: introducing the GATE as a service

With the support of experts and literature reviews, the idea of the GATE has been realised as a service with dual benefits:

(1) group-specific OS guidelines are collected from OS trainers to expand the data collection for OS guidelines (which will be further developed into standards based on majority responses) and

(2) simultaneously, existing (already majority-named) guidelines are shared with these trainers, allowing them to review and amend their training if necessary.

Timeline of the Open Science Learning Gate's Origin in the NERQ_OS Group

May 2023: NERQ_OS initiated discussions on devising an educational map tailored to varied training needs, collating essential training resources for different target groups to showcase the results in the September NERQ general meeting.

June 2023: NERQ_OS pursued the objectives set in May, focusing on developing a learning material exchange platform. This involved gathering appropriate resources for each target group, extending the network to obtain more learning materials, and including the role of Data Scholarship Librarian to the Data Steward/Data Librarian category.

July 2023: A discourse on collecting further ideas pertinent to OS, such as the role of a Data Ethics guardian. Additionally, the terminology related to positions and the criticality of skills for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) were emphasised.

August 2023: Conversations about potential collaboration with the Open Science Capacity Building Index and initiating a workshop to discuss the legal aspects of creating e-learning materials. Detailed plans for the upcoming NERQ_OS workshop in September 2023 were also laid out.

September 2023: Detailed planning for the NERQ_OS workshop, including preparing relevant questions for stakeholders based on their OS learning resources presentations. Finalising the workshop's agenda and critical topics also marked in September of 2023.

November 2023: Hosted meetings focusing on Research Integrity, Open Science, reproducibility, equality, and FAIR principles. The events included keynotes, workshops, and discussions hosted by field experts.

December 2023 - April 2024: NERQ_OS conducted a comprehensive literature review, including references to OS's eight pillars and various resources related to OS and Research Integrity.

May 2024: Discussions on effectively addressing various stakeholders in OS, consolidating information on OS training, and designing the GATE service for principal collection and OS training badging. Moreover, plans for the launch of the GATE were sketched.

Timeline of the GATE's interactions towards the official launch of the GATE service in June 2024

NERQ_OS followed a comprehensive 2024 roadmap between August 2024 and December 2024:

In June 2024, NERQ_OS celebrated the successful kick-off of the GATE at the WCRI2024. Key topics discussed included potential collaborations with several collaborators, improvements on the service, and creating a badge to recognise high-quality training. Reporting of the officially launched GATE service can be found here: [World Conference of Research Integrity 2024 \(WCRI\)](#).

4 An annual GATE Report

In addition to the above, the importance of so-called annual GATE reports developed in the last few months. These GATE reports will track the dynamic evolution of OS guidelines and their development via the GATE collection. This function will ensure the continued relevance and up-to-dateness of the GATE service and will provide trainers with a continuous list of current OS guidelines.

In October 2024, we presented the GATE report idea to the European Commission. We discussed that the GATE reports will collect OS training and guidelines over the coming years and inform and update the OS community on current OS guidelines (based on majority nomination and expert evaluation) in annual GATE Reports. They will also inform trainers participating in the GATE and thus support high-quality OS training. This makes the GATE an effective European tool to support the harmonisation of OS guidelines and to promote high-quality capacity building in OS.

In parallel, we have continued to refine the GATE service with experts and further expanded the data collection (OS guidelines) in workshops so that the GATE currently reflects a clear picture of the OS guidelines. Since November, we have collaborated with OpenAIRE and will further expand the data collection with their Community of Practice for Trainers in January. Last but not least, RIOS (Amsterdam) will host a GATE workshop in January 2025.

For the most recent updates and additional information regarding the GATE, we encourage everyone to visit the [Open Science Learning Gate community on Zenodo](#).

5 Collaboration with the Open Science Learning Gate

OS experts and supporters can collaborate with the GATE by following several structured steps:

1. **Use the GATE service:** As an OS trainer, you can use the GATE service to add your OS guidelines, add your voice to the GATE report and optimise your training resources. The service is designed to help you systematically integrate and align your guidelines with the research community, ensuring consistency and quality in your training offerings—as demonstrated by the GATE badge. You can visit the [GATE service](#) here.
2. **Connect your Projects, Repositories, and Efforts to the GATE:** Reach out to Julia Priess-Buchheit and Marie Alavi to connect your collaborative efforts with the GATE. Engaging with these key contacts might facilitate collaboration and integration and provide opportunities.
3. **Become a supporter of the GATE report:** As an OS-supporting organisation, you can sponsor the GATE to actively support high-quality capacity building and be a visible organisation that fosters and connects to the newest OS developments.